

Autism Spectrum Disorder: Etiology, Recovery, and Prevention

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Abstract

The etiology of autism remains elusive in conventional medicine, with varying ages of onset and unclear causative factors. However, alternative perspectives suggest that spiritual influences may play a significant role in the development of autism. Dharma Master Jun Hong Lu, through His Dharma teachings, has provided insights into the underlying spiritual mechanisms contributing to autism, particularly emphasizing the impact of spirit possession and karmic consequences. Karmic factors associated with autism include killing karma from abortion, animal slaughter, and ancestral karma. Additionally, playing spiritual games, exposure to inappropriate content online, receiving a grandiose name, and disharmony between parents can contribute to the development of autism. Regardless of the cause, autistic children are occupied by spirits, which must be ascended to heal the children. Case reports within the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door community support the effectiveness of these spiritual interventions in treating autism, offering hope to families struggling with this complex disorder.

Keywords: Autism Spectrum Disorder, Karma, Spirit, Little House, Rehabilitation.

Introduction

Autism, formally known as Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), is a complex neurodevelopmental condition characterized by a wide range of challenges in social interaction, communication, and behaviors. It is called a "spectrum" disorder because the severity and manifestation of symptoms can vary significantly among patients. Some patients may have significant intellectual disabilities, while others may excel in areas such as art, music, or mathematics.

The prevalence of autism has increased over the past few decades, with the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) estimating that approximately 1 in 36 children in the United States is diagnosed with ASD [1]. This rise in diagnosis is partly attributed to broader diagnostic criteria, increased awareness, and better screening practices [2].

Autism is typically diagnosed in early childhood, although some people may not receive a diagnosis until later in life. Although the exact causes of autism are not fully understood, it is believed to result from a combination of genetic and environmental factors [3]. ASD has proven to be highly enigmatic due to the diversity of its underlying genetic causes and the huge variability in symptom presentation [4]. Research indicates that there are certain genetic mutations associated with the condition, though no single gene is responsible for all cases [5].

Interventions for autism are most effective when started early and tailored to the individual's needs [6]. These may include behavioral therapy, speech and language therapy, occupational therapy, and educational support. Some patients who have severe intellectual disability may experience uncontrolled aggression, causing serious injury or harm to others, and the therapeutic ineffectiveness of traditional pharmacological and behavioral treatment may aggravate symptoms [7].

Despite recovery from autistic disorder is rare, there are a few reports of recovery. One case even involved spontaneous recovery from autistic disorder without any intervention within 13 days [8]. However, the author

acknowledged that recovery from autistic disorder is unexpected and unexplained. Another case involved a rapid and complete recovery from an ASD after treatment for *Aspergillus* with the antifungal drugs Itraconazole and Sporanox [9]. However, there have been no subsequent follow-up reports to replicate the findings.

Basically, the medical community currently generally believes that there is no cure for autism [10].

Now, the belief that there is no cure for autism may no longer be accurate. In a previous article, we reported a case where autism was cured by a mother practicing the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door [11]. In this article, we will present more cases where ASD was cured through these Dharma practices [12], further deepening our understanding of the etiology of autism.

Etiology

The etiology of ASD is not currently known in medicine, and the age of onset is also variable [13].

When medicine encounters difficulties in helping patients, Master Lu enlightens us that Dharma may offer solutions. Below are two live Q&A dialogues in which Master Lu unveiled the underlying mechanisms of autism and provided effective solutions for treating it.

Q&A 1: A mother's abortion leads to a child's autism and 19 years of silence (excerpt) [14]

This is a Totem Reading session from the Hong Kong Dharma Conference on May 1, 2012. During the session, a mother brought her daughter to ask Master Lu about the cause of the girl's ASD.

Asker: Respected Guan Yin Bodhisattva and Master. I have a girl born in 1993, Year of the Rooster. Could you please see if she has any spirits on her?

Master: Oh, this young girl has a spirit being on her. I'm telling you, she often doesn't talk much and is very introverted.

Asker: Yes, yes.

Master: I'm telling you, this girl often says strange things. There is indeed a spirit on her, and it's affecting her mind, right?

Asker: Yes, yes, it's been 19 years now.

Master: I'm telling you, you must quickly recite the Little House for her because the spirit of the child you aborted is on her, do you understand?

Asker: Yes, I understand.

Master: Recite for her karmic creditor diligently.

Asker: How should I do it, and how many should I recite?

Master: Oh, you don't know? Hmm.

Asker: I'm a beginner.

Master: A beginner.

Asker: Yes.

Master: Since you just began, start by reciting 21 Little Houses, alright? Recite 49 times the *Great Compassion Mantra* daily, 27 times the *Heart Sutra*, and 49 times the *Xiao Zai Ji Xiang Shen Zhou*. Also, can you perform animal liberation? Make a vow.

Asker: I'm already liberating animals.

Master: Make a vow: "If my daughter's health improves, I will be grateful to the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva. I will do such and such." At the very least, stop eating live sea animals. On the 1st and 15th days of the lunar month, can you be a vegetarian?

Asker: Yes, as long as it can save my daughter, I will follow your instructions.

Master: I'm telling you, quickly help her ascend this spirit. She has been like this for many years, and I'm telling you, it's pitiful. Her mind is sometimes clear and sometimes not.

Asker: Yes, yes, it's like that.

Master: There's hope. I'm telling you, her life is not in danger. I see that there's still a year and a half left. If you recite diligently, she will have a turning point. If not, she might completely forget everything. Do you understand?

Asker: Yes.

Master: If you diligently perform animal liberation and make vows in the next year and a half, I can tell you, she will be saved.

Asker: Thank you, Master. I will definitely follow your instructions. I even dreamed that Master would call me and tell me to bring my daughter here. This is the only place that can save her.

Master: Yes, that was my Dharmakaya. Also, I'm telling you, the child next to you has issues too. Do you understand? The child next to you.

Asker: This is my daughter.

Master: Oh, this is your daughter, right?

Asker: Yes.

Master: Oh, I thought it was another boy.

Asker: It's her, it's her.

Master: Alright, no problem then. This girl doesn't talk much, almost never. Let me give her some blessings so she can speak right away. Don't say anything. What's her name?

Asker: She was previously registered as TQ.

Master: Don't talk; it's not you. Put the microphone near her mouth. Don't talk. TQ, TQ.

Asker: Her name has been changed to TXM. Everyone calls her XM.

Master: Ah, XM, XM. Hey XM. Are you alright? Are you alright? Not alright? Can you say something? Let Master teach you how to speak, okay?

If you speak, everyone will be happy. If you speak, everyone will applaud. XM, alright? Say something. Can you talk? Say something. Guan Yin Bodhisattva is here to save you.

Asker's Daughter: Bodhisattva.

Asker: Thank you, Master. Thank you, Guan Yin Bodhisattva.

Master: See, she's happy now. Do you listen to Master? Do you listen to Master?

Asker's Daughter: Yes.

Asker: Thank you, Master. Gratitude to Guan Yin Bodhisattva.

Master: No problem, she can be saved, alright?

Asker: Thank you, Master.

Master: Recite Buddhist scriptures diligently.

Asker: Yes, thank you. Gratitude, and gratitude to all my fellow practitioners for giving me this opportunity. Thank you, everyone.

Q&A 2. An autistic little girl was possessed by a spirit due to playing a spiritual game [15]

This is a Totem Reading Program held at the Los Angeles Dharma Conference on September 11, 2016. During the session, a father brought his daughter to ask Master Lu about the cause of the girl's ASD and how to recover.

Asker: I respectfully ask Master Lu to take a look at my daughter. Does she have a spirit in her? She was born in 1996, the Year of the Rat.

Master: Of course, there is a big spirit. She often loses her temper, likes to lock herself in her room at night, doesn't want to talk to others, and doesn't want to communicate with you.

Asker: Yes, that's exactly right.

Master: You need to help her recite Buddhist scriptures to ascend this spirit. If you don't, her autism will worsen. She already has autism.

Asker: Yes.

Master: She was fine when she was young, but the spirit possessed her later.

Asker: Yes, it happened in the past few years. Is it a family member or an outsider?

Master: It's an outsider, attracted by her. She played a spiritual game, and a ghost possessed her. Now, there is a male spirit on her.

Asker: Yes, she feels it, and she can also see it.

Master: She often wakes up suddenly and sees a shadow at the foot of her bed.

Asker: Yes.

Master: Let me tell you, this kind of illness cannot be cured except through reciting Buddhist scriptures.

Asker: I have just started.

Master: Have you become vegetarian?

Asker: I eat half meat, half vegetarian.

Master: You need to make a vow for her. Does she eat a vegetarian diet? Tell her not to eat living beings. She was a good child, very obedient in the past, and treated you very well. After the spirit possessed her, she started getting sick.

Asker: Yes.

Master: Sometimes she also has convulsions.

Asker: Yes.

Master: Her temper flares up suddenly and without reason because of the ghost on her.

Asker: Yes.

Master: She might even call you a ghost.

Asker: What should I do?

Master: Are you a ghost? You're not, so just recite the Buddhist scriptures well. I'll give her some energy. She smiles and feels happy. See, her face has changed.

Asker: Yes, just now it (spirit) was still on her.

Master: I should call you "Master Lu," as you already know it—"It (spirit) was still on her just now, but now it's gone." Sometimes, when I speak, there is a force that drives the spirit away. This little girl is actually very pretty, well-behaved, and diligent. You are also very partial to her.

Asker: Yes.

Master: You owe her a lot from your past life, so you have to repay her. Her relationship with her mother is not good.

Asker: Yes.

Master: There are no other problems. She just likes to hear good things about herself, which makes her happy because the ghost on her likes to hear good things. So in the future, you need to say to her, "You're so pretty," or "Oh, how good you are." This will make her happy, but in reality, it is the ghost that is happy. You need to help her recite Buddhist scriptures—360 Little Houses in total—and release 2,400 fish.

Asker: Okay.

Master: Also, let her get some sun every day. Her back should be in the sun, but not her face, as she has a serious deficiency in Yang energy. Other than that, have her recite the *Heart Sutra* and *Great Compassion Mantra* daily. Let me tell you, the spirit often presses on her when she sleeps.

Asker: Yes, sometimes she can't sleep at night.

Master: She screams; she often sees this male spirit, and he strangles her, coming onto her body.

Asker: Yes, sometimes she says she can't breathe.

Master: See? That's why I tell you, you must not offend people, and even more so, you must not offend ghosts. You already harbored grudges against others, you must not harbor grudges against animals. If you kill them, their souls (spirits) will possess you. If you kill a duck or a chicken, it (its spirit) will possess you too. Many people, just before they die, experience severe pain, and their screams sound like the animal they killed. This is because they slaughtered a cow when they were young, and as they are about to die in the hospital, they feel the pain as if they are being reincarnated into a cow. So do not harbor grudges against animals. After reciting these Little Houses, the little girl will gradually get better.

Asker: Thank you, Master Lu.

Master: Be particularly careful about her gynecological issues and her feet, as her joints are not in good condition. If you have her recite Buddhist scriptures, she will get better and better. She has a lot of self-esteem; the ghost on her cares very much about his face. So just recite the Buddhist scriptures well, and there's no need to say anything else.

Asker: Okay, thank you, Master Lu.

Master: Make a vow that if she recovers, you will go on stage to share your experience, just like others, to inspire more people to practice Dharma. She will recover even faster.

From the two dialogues above, we can conclude that ASD is caused by the presence of one or more spirits occupying the patient. These ghosts, often

respectfully referred to as "spirits," can be an aborted child (Q&A 1) or a deceased adult (Q&A 2). In fact, Master Lu's Totem Reading Program often reveals that abortion or miscarriage is one of the most common causes of autism [16,17,18].

In addition to the spirits of deceased humans causing autism, Master Lu revealed many other factors that contribute to the etiology of autism. This includes killing animals [19], destroying entire forests and killing many sentient beings [20], consuming live sea animals during pregnancy [11], and ancestral karma [21].

Other contributing factors include the deceased ancestor [22], the past-life lover [23], animal spirit [24], exposure to negative content online [25], and playing spiritual games (Q&A 2). Furthermore, frequent parental quarrels, and living in a house that is perpetually dark with excessive negative energy, often attract spirits [26]. Additionally, giving a child a name that is too grand, potentially overwhelming them, can also lead to autism [27].

Lastly, frequent visits to places where spirits often linger [28], can easily result in spirit possession.

When a spirit possesses a child, it exerts control over the brain, disrupting neurodevelopment and potentially leading to conditions like autism. As this is a spiritual illness, the appropriate treatment involves helping the spirit ascend. Once the external spirit departs, the patient's natural healing process can resume.

Results

Case 1. Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door cured my daughter's autism

I used to be a very rational person who believed in science, but after personally experiencing certain events, I have changed my beliefs. Now, I believe in Guan Yin Bodhisattva and the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door.

My daughter is currently six years old now. She had emotional disorders. She has been difficult to care for since she was a child. She often cried, screamed, and threw tantrums, making the atmosphere at home very tense. One day, my wife told me that she noticed signs of autism in our daughter! At first, I strongly opposed this idea, thinking that she was still young and would improve as she grew older.

However, by the time she was three and a half years old, her issues had not improved but had become more severe! We then took her for a professional evaluation, and the diagnosis was that she was highly sensitive and exhibited autistic tendencies. At that moment, I finally accepted the reality and began professional treatment for her.

We spent three years accompanying her through therapies similar to physical therapy. Although there were some physical improvements, she remained highly sensitive emotionally, often screaming and throwing tantrums. Even her younger brother was afraid to get close to her. We were deeply saddened by her emotional issues.

During this treatment period, a pediatrician even prescribed a strictly controlled medication for my daughter. This was a psychiatric drug used to control the central nervous system, meant for children with autism and attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) to help stabilize their emotions. However, we did not dare to use this special medication because it had severe side effects. For example, it could suppress appetite, requiring another medication to stimulate it. Additionally, it could make a person mentally sluggish, and with prolonged use, the dosage would need to be increased for it to remain effective. As a result, my wife threw the medication

into the trash, as we did not want to solve our daughter's problem this way.

My wife had to care for two children every day, and by the end of the day, she was exhausted. Coupled with our daughter's emotional instability, constant tantrums, crying, and screaming, she felt an overwhelming sense of pressure and helplessness. This long-term stress made her feel like she was on the verge of collapse! She often couldn't sleep at night and began to feel she had depression. Many times, she cried and knelt before the Buddhist altar, pleading for help from Guan Yin Bodhisattva. I believe it was the suffering and helplessness of a mother that made the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva hear my wife's plea for help.

One day, my wife saw an advertisement in the newspaper for Master Lu's upcoming Dharma Conference in Kuala Lumpur. When she saw Master Lu's kind and compassionate photo in the advertisement, she felt an inexplicable emotion and trust, leaving a deep impression in her heart. Coincidentally, two days later, a friend introduced us to Master Lu's Dharma Conference and gave us entry tickets and a book titled *Totem World*. Because of this, my wife believed it was Guan Yin Bodhisattva's guidance.

After attending the Dharma Conference, I personally only found Master Lu's ability to read totems to be miraculous! I didn't have much understanding of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, nor did I think it would solve my daughter's problems.

In November 2011, my wife started reciting Buddhist scriptures. Three days later, she dreamed of deceased relatives. This made her believe even more in the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. At that time, I hadn't started reciting Buddhist scriptures because I was still half-believing and half-doubting the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door.

It wasn't until my wife told a fellow Buddhist practitioner about our daughter's problems that she responded, saying that our daughter must have a spirit attached to her and suggested that we recite Little Houses. It was under these circumstances that I started reciting Buddhist scriptures.

The practitioner suggested that we start with reciting 49 Little Houses and make a grand vow to Bodhisattva, stating that we would share our daughter's example to inspire more sentient beings. On that day, after making the vow at the Guan Yin Hall in Kuala Lumpur, my wife and I went to pick up our daughter from kindergarten. To our astonishment, as soon as our daughter got in the car, she asked in a puzzled tone, "Ah? Are you going to recite 49 Little Houses?"

My wife and I immediately exchanged glances, realizing that it was the spirit attached to our daughter speaking to us. We were utterly shocked! Although we didn't show it on our faces, we truly felt that making the vow was indeed effective, and Bodhisattva was genuinely compassionate!

Because of that one sentence from my daughter, my previously skeptical belief in the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door became firmly belief, and the subsequent miraculous responses further solidified my belief in the existence of another realm.

In two months, we recited a total of 55 Little Houses for our daughter's karmic creditor. We noticed significant improvements: our daughter's relationship with her younger brother became very good, and they often played together. This was a rare occurrence in the past. We were happy for a while, but her emotional fluctuations continued.

In April 2012, Malaysia's best-selling magazine *Feminine* conducted a long-distance interview with Master Lu. Compassionately, Master Lu made an exception and read the totem for my daughter. He said that there was a spirit

in my daughter's body, which was an aborted child. The spirit resided in her brain, causing her autism. He told us that the spirit in my daughter's brain was the child my mother had aborted. He even described my mother's appearance. Master Lu also pointed out that my daughter was very stubborn, refusing to listen even to her parents, which was indeed the case.

Master Lu instructed us to recite 17 Little Houses for our daughter's karmic creditor, promising that there would be significant improvement afterward. Then, we should recite an additional 375 Little Houses to resolve the problem entirely. However, since the spirit had been in my daughter's body for a long time, even after completing the recitation, it would take some time for her to gradually recover. But Master Lu assured us that our daughter would get better and even saw her lively demeanor in the future.

After the totem reading, I felt much more at ease, as if I had already seen the light. So, my wife and I spent four months reciting a total of 392 Little Houses for our daughter's karmic creditor.

Everything happened just as Master Lu had predicted. My daughter's condition improved significantly, she became more lively, and her face was filled with more and more smiles. The siblings often played and laughed together, and our home was filled with joy instead of noise. The most noticeable change was that my daughter's habit of muttering to herself unconsciously disappeared! Seeing her improvement, my wife and I were overjoyed, filled with Dharma joy and gratitude towards Guan Yin Bodhisattva and Master Lu's compassion.

In conclusion, I want to express my deepest gratitude to the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva, the compassionate Master Lu, and the fellow practitioners of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. I vow to perform more merits and virtues and to save more sentient beings having an affinity with Buddha.

Dharma practitioner: W39

Comments

1. Before practicing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, one would generally rarely dream of deceased individuals because they know you can't repay your debts. However, once you start practicing this Dharma Door, your karmic creditors immediately become aware that you now can repay your debts. They will quickly appear in your dreams to remind you to pay what you owe. Three days after the author's wife began reciting Buddhist scriptures, she dreamed of deceased relatives, indicating that the soul continues to exist after death. This confirms Master Lu's teachings and proves that Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is real and not illusory.
2. Once a person makes a vow, especially in the Guan Yin Hall or in front of a Buddhist altar, all beings, including spirits and deities, are aware of it. After the practitioner and his wife made a vow at the Guan Yin Hall, the spirit attached to their daughter immediately knew. This once again proves the real existence of the spiritual realm.

Case 2. An autistic child with ADHD attends school normally via Dharma

I started studying Buddhism at the end of April 2016, initially solely for the sake of my son. In early April 2016, my child was diagnosed with autistic developmental delay at the provincial children's hospital.

Before heading to the hospital, he had been discouraged from kindergarten after staying there for 5 days. During those 5 days, he slept on the floor every

day, not eating or drinking, and was locked in the miscellaneous room for lunch breaks. I was told this by a teacher when I did the withdrawal for him. In fact, my son was dissuaded from returning to school. I can probably guess the reason in my heart because he has almost no communication with others. According to the old people in my family, if a child opens his mouth late, he will grow up into a noble person. Coupled with the fact that I was busy in business, I never paid much attention to his problems. After he was diagnosed with autism in one hospital, we took him to the most reputable children's hospital in the city. This was for a double test. He was diagnosed with moderate to severe autism.

His cognitive abilities were equivalent to that of a 1.5-year-old, even though he was actually 4 years old at the time, with the comprehension level of an 8-month-old infant. After 2 months of rehabilitation in the hospital, he did not make progress. He could not comprehend the most basic concepts of cats, dogs, rabbits and tigers.

In May 2016, I traveled to the local temple to pray to the Guan Yin Bodhisattva, hoping She could save my child. After returning from the temple, I couldn't sleep all day long. I was a little depressed, couldn't think straight, and washed my face with tears every day. I argued with my husband because he didn't care about the child's condition. He said the big deal was to keep him as a pet for the rest of his life. But I didn't think so. As long as I wasn't at work, I started chanting the holy name of Guan Yin Bodhisattva, reciting hundreds and thousands of times a day.

The Child's Specific Symptoms at That Time

1. In terms of language, he can only call grandma.
2. Not sleeping, loud shouting, high energy level.
3. No response to eye contact, wandering; no response to name calling; no idea what his name is; not able to distinguish between male and female.
4. No sense of safety rules; running randomly once outside.
5. Stereotypical behavior; unwilling to wear new clothes and shoes; walking a fixed route, not accepting change; afraid of shaving hair, squatting on the toilet, and sounds of crying and firecrackers, etc.
6. Big temper; not coming home at night but going out in the middle of the night.
7. Talking to himself and liking laughing, as if being punctuated by others with laughing points.
8. Self-harming behavior, biting himself, and bumping his head against the wall.
9. Loving looking at wheels and things that turn in circles, such as fans, wheels, etc.; very hyperactive.
10. Picky at food and not like vegetables; asocial; unlike going to other people's homes; not allowing others to enter my homes.
11. Unable to perform gross and fine motor movements.

One late at night, I looked up information on autism on the Internet. By chance, I came across an article about the miraculous recovery of autism by Buddhism on a Buddhist practitioner's blog. I was immediately fascinated and instantly left a message to the Buddhist, hoping to study Buddhism.

As soon as I started practicing Buddhism, I made 2 vows. I would be a vegetarian for the rest of my life. On the 1st and 15th days of each lunar month, I perform life liberation.

When more than 100 Little Houses were recited for his karmic creditors, my son showed significant improvement. He began to understand picture books, differentiate between similar vehicles, and speak more. He also reduced his habit of eating boogers and biting his fingernails, and his sleep improved compared to before.

In October, I traveled to a fellow Buddhist practitioner's home to ask for a Bodhisattva statue. On the way back, my son suddenly called out to me a few times, "Mom". This was the first time in over 4 years that my child called me mom. I have been waiting for this "mom" for more than 4 years. I am so grateful that I cannot describe it in words. I am very, very grateful to Guan Yin Bodhisattva for bringing such a wonderful Dharma Door to earth.

On the night of Spring Festival Eve 2017, when I offered the Bodhisattva the first incense, I made a few vows. I will convince sentient beings to practice Buddhism using my experiences. I pray to the Bodhisattva to bless my child for entering kindergarten in 2017. I would release 1,000 fish on behalf of my child after the Spring Festival. Besides being a vegetarian, I would not kill beings. I would donate to print the Buddhist scriptures and distribute them to sentient beings for free. I would perform merits and virtues by donating money to charity. In the early morning of the Spring Festival, I dreamed that my child had climbed up from a deep mud puddle. He sat in a classroom with 2 very kind teachers interacting with him. When I woke up from the dream, I instantly realized Guan Yin Bodhisattva had blessed him. He would definitely be able to go to kindergarten.

On the 16th day of the Lunar New Year, he was smoothly enrolled in kindergarten as I dreamed. For my child to be emotionally stable in kindergarten, I specifically recited the *Heart Sutra* 49x2 times for him. This was in addition to the daily *Heart Sutra* recitation 49 times for him. I hope he doesn't cry in kindergarten. I made a vow to recite the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* 10,000 times specifically for him, hoping his ADHD would get better.

In August 2017, I fulfilled my vow and appeared at the Malaysian Dharma Conference to make a presentation. Just as I was about to finish my lecture, I turned around and saw Master Lu. Master Lu was standing at the back door with a smile listening to what I had said. At that moment, I saw compassion, kindness, and amiability in Master Lu's eyes. I was so excited when Master Lu came towards me. Master, you saved my child. Several times I wanted to turn around and hug You and cry to express my gratitude.

After I returned from the Conference, I still tried my best to recite the Buddhist scriptures, never daring to slake off. I actively helped fellow practitioners set up Buddhist altars. I actively participated in various life-release activities. In addition, I propagated Dharma in my own way to save sentient beings.

It was not only my child who learned phonetics in 2018 in the older kindergarten class, but also addition and subtraction as well within 20. Importantly, his ADHD disappeared. The teacher said that he could sit peacefully in the classroom and would not run around the teacher and classroom anymore. He can participate in extracurricular activities at school. His bad habits from his previous life became more evident as he talked more and more. I used to be anxious when he didn't talk, but I was angry every day when he did. There must have been deep grievances between him and me in our previous lives. He was incompatible with me, biting me, hitting me, being stubborn with me, urging me to die, "hurry up and die, die quickly," or telling me to shut up, and asking me to get out. One day, I was so angry that I cried

out in front of the Buddhist altar. I couldn't tell my parents about my suffering. They were too old to help, and I was afraid they would annoy me if I did. I really don't want to recite Buddhist scripture to my child anymore. I am too tired. I get up at 4:30 morning and go to bed at midnight. When I felt desperate enough, I committed suicide 4 times. I wanted to be run over by a car. I bought sleeping pills and rat poison and would like to die quickly. After crying that night, I got to bed early. The next morning, I dreamed of the Master. I told Him about the child's condition in my dream. Master Lu kindly came toward me, looked at my child and said, "Come to the Dharma Conference. I will treat the child." The next day, I woke up from the dream and still felt incredible. Two or three days later, I suddenly received a notice to hold a Dharma Conference. To verify the truth of my dream, I determined to take my child to the Dharma Conference. At the conference, my child was honored to be blessed by Buddha and Bodhisattva: Master Lu read his totem. I was deeply grateful to the Master that my dream was fulfilled. Buddha's teachings are true. Master Lu is my father, making me feel safer and warmer than I have ever felt before.

With the blessing of Guan Yin Bodhisattva, my child successfully passed the first-grade interview in 2019 and entered a public school. In the 2nd grade, his intelligence grew to another level. He scored over 80 points in language and mathematics in the winter vacation exam (the full score is 100 points). My family had a happy Lunar New Year.

In the 4th grade, my child began to do daily recitation of Buddhist scriptures. His language improved by leaps and bounds. His thoughts became active. He had no problem interacting, playing, and communicating with his classmates.

At last, I'd like to share some of my experiences studying Buddhism in the following.

1. Reciting the Buddhist scriptures and eliminating karmic obstacles are the most important.
2. For children with serious illnesses, parents must make big vows. Big vows can give the child blessings and make them recover faster.
3. If possible, set up a Buddhist altar at home. Setting up a Buddhist altar has immense merits and virtues. You can get many blessings. Don't rush to get a result. Plowing without asking for a harvest. After sowing seeds, fertilize and water them. They need time to grow.
4. Guard your body, speech and mind. Refrain from creating new karma. Removing greed, hatred and delusion is the key. Do not let the small merits and virtues you just accrue leak away.
5. Purify the body and the mind honestly. Only by cultivating yourself like a Bodhisattva, can you behave like a Bodhisattva to save your child.
6. So long as you are sincere in cultivating your mind, your prayers will be answered. If your thoughts are sincere, the Buddha will respond. According to this saying, we must believe that Buddha and Bodhisattva really exist. Only if you believe, can you be saved.
7. Do not seek supernatural powers, dreams, and totem readings. Regardless of whether the dream hints or not, or the totem reading, we always use the Five Golden Buddhist Practices to eliminate karmic obstacles. We also recite Buddhist scriptures to pay off karmic debts. There is no shortcut to take.
8. Try hard to repent of karmic obstacles created in this life.

Dharma Practitioner: N40

Comments

Master Lu advised us that family members should recite the *Mantra to Untie Karmic Knots*, as those who live together often carry grievances from past lives or this life. Although the child recovered from autism, the unresolved grievances between him and his mother remained.

Case 3. The autistic son is sunnier after encountering Buddhism

The reason I practice Buddhism is because of my son. He was a severely autistic child. Before his birth, I always felt my life was going well. After his birth, my life was stuck.

When he was 2-3 years old, he still could not initiate speech. He was examined at the local hospital and diagnosed as autistic. I remember looking up information online. The more I read, the more I couldn't accept it. How come a good child needs a lifetime of rehabilitation and can't be cured? When he was born, everything was normal, completely by growth and development laws. In the developmental status column of the pediatric examination data book, it was often written: middle to upper. When he was 7-8 months old, he babbled and made sounds, was very active, liked to climb high and low, and was particularly energetic. From waking up in the morning he stayed active until the evening.

A long road of medical rehabilitation, special school, sensory therapy, and sand tray followed. Although the money was spent, the effect was minimal. He occasionally made simple sounds. However, he would not open his mouth if not practiced for a period of time. He forgot what we had taught him after a while. He has cognitive impairment, learning disabilities, and no imitation ability. His eyes can be right on ours for only a few seconds. He seemed to have problems all over his body to me. Sometimes he cried wildly for no reason. How pitiful he was! I could not help him. I did not know why he cried. I did not know how to coax him to calm down. It is mental torture to care for such a type of child. I once thought of leaving this world with him because it was too painful and difficult. I often asked myself why I had to give birth to such a child when I hadn't done anything bad in my life.

In the 6 months before I encountered the Dharma, I was especially helpless, desperate and anxious about the future. During that time, I was also traveling to a brain hospital. Initially, I thought my child's autism was a joke from heaven. He was over 5 years old but had no language or cognition. Nevertheless, I didn't realize that what came along with it was even more unbearable. He had epilepsy and even had a shadow on his brain. The doctor said the shadow might be a tumor or a brain lesion. I was unable to accept the fact but could only tear silently and helplessly. I am grateful to the Bodhisattva! The final examination revealed that the shadow on his brain was just scar tissue.

One day, I received a message from a parent: "Dear, do you believe in Buddhism?" Since then, my child's destiny and mine have completely changed. Through studying Buddhism, I slowly found the answer that everything is karma.

When I was pregnant with my child, I ate fish soup almost every day to enhance my nutrition. After giving birth, I stewed chicken and fish soups to promote breast milk secretion. When the child was one month old, according to our local customs, we invited guests to a large banquet. We served 60-70 tables of live fish and sea animals to the guests. My mother worked on a pigeon farm when she was young. She helped slaughter pigeons to provide for restaurants every day. A few years ago, she opened a small farm. Every

day, she killed animals for guests. It is all the result of our delusions, ignorance, and unknowledge of the law of karma. We have committed so many killings. The karma was retributed to my son. We hereby repent of the beings we have harmed, and we are really sorry. Killing karma is really a matter of retribution for three generations.

In January 2019, I began reciting the Little House. On September 19th of the lunar calendar, I made a vow to release 100,000 living creatures. In February 2020, I made a vow to become a full vegetarian for life.

Because the child's symptoms are particularly numerous, I have eliminated his karma generally. As a way of repaying his karmic creditors, I didn't focus on his specific symptoms. Now, let me briefly describe the changes in the child over the past 3 years:

1. Following my practice of Buddhism, he was able to mimic the teacher's movements to complete simple movements along with the song. This had never happened before.
2. Previously, he didn't want to turn off the water after taking a shower, which caused me headaches. He would play with the water for a long time until he had played enough. He would cry loudly if forced to leave. Suddenly one day when I had practiced Buddhism for 3 months, he turned off the water after showering by following our directions. At first, I thought it was strange how he was so well-behaved that day. I found that he was able to end up happily in the bath afterward.
3. Six months after I practiced Buddhism, he switched to another rehab over 10 minutes from home. In the new rehab, he was able to pronounce simple syllables and personal nouns steadily in just 3 months, "Dad," "Mom," "Hello Auntie!" etc. In the following 3 months, one afternoon, his teacher sent me a short video. He imitated the teacher and said, "Mommy, I love you!" Watching this video, I cried and moved to tears. I waited for this "I love you" for 6 whole years. In this life, I did not expect to be able to hear such a wonderful language. Things for others' children can simply be learned, but how much effort and cost do we have to pay for such a short few words? I believe that only those families with such a child at home can understand this hardship.
4. Since age 4, I have been scared and panicked whenever he had a fever. During the fever, he would appear briefly in seizure convulsions, roll his eyes, and instantly turn his lips purple. The doctor recommended sedative medication. The drug caused him to become inexplicably excited. As his excitement reached its peak, he became exhausted and fell asleep. As a result, we could not sleep when he was feverish. Before his fever went down, we dared not let him sleep because each time the convulsions attacked when he was sleepy. However, since 2019 when I began practicing Buddhism, he has not taken a single sedative pill. Only one time his fever was too high and rose too quickly. We took him to the hospital for observation. He fell asleep and did not have a seizure even when he was 38 degrees. Every time the child had a fever, I silently asked Guan Yin Bodhisattva to bless him and recover smoothly. Additionally, I vowed to recite Little Houses for his karmic creditors and release the fish that were being slaughtered. In this way, we have survived these 3 years. Guan Yin

Bodhisattva is so compassionate! Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is really effective and true.

Over the past 3 years, I have witnessed so many efficacious events and miracles. The child I miscarried has ascended. Whether big or small, I have passed calamities by making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, or releasing fish. I am grateful for the compassionate enlightenment I received through my dreams from the Bodhisattva.

Now my son is a capable, sunny and handsome boy. His language is getting richer and richer. He can sing children's songs, memorize poems and recite mantras. In addition to being a warm boy at home, he helps with chores around the house. Moreover, studying Buddhism has enabled us to meet many kind and patient teachers and coaches, so that my child can make gains in all major physical sports. Once again, I am grateful to the Bodhisattva for Her compassionate blessing on my child.

Finally, I would like to share my own feelings for the past 3 years. I know that my karmic obstacles are deep and heavy. At the beginning of my Buddhism study, my husband said that I was too addicted, my father-in-law advised that I was too young to be a vegetarian, and my mother told me to let it be, but I was firm in my choice. I even ate a bowl of white rice for every meal at my in-laws' house and felt very content. There was no material thing to exchange for my child's healthy growth. With my own perseverance and by reciting the *Heart Sutra* and the *Mantra to Untie Karmic Knots* to them, my husband, though disagreeing with my Buddhist studies, would help me to cook vegetarian dishes, my father-in-law would occasionally order a vegetarian dish for me, and my mother would invite me to go to release lives. At the beginning, I was half-hearted about Buddhism. However, autism and epilepsy are medical problems, and Buddhism is the last opportunity I can grab. In the first year of practicing Buddhism, at special times of the year, the child cried a lot for no reason. This was a very challenging test for me. I would have a doubtful heart. I was really sorry for the Bodhisattva. Once, I hoped to look for so-called scientific intervention methods. It was really too ignorant and foolish. I had forgotten that the Master had said that the success of an event lies in karma and not in ability. I had forgotten that the words "Virtue is not worthy of a position". If I don't accumulate virtue and blessings, how can I deserve a healthy child? I had forgotten, that once attached to affliction, the child would enter into a karmic destiny, and ultimately can not be liberated.

Heaven has given each of us, each day, 24 hours. The Bodhisattva gives each of us, the same Dharma Gems.

One's destiny lies in one's own choices. No matter what difficulties or obstacles you encounter, treat them as a test. You just have to hold on to your belief that I want to learn Buddhism and recite Buddhist scriptures. It was this belief that made me persevere at the beginning. Then, I can see my child's progress today, bit by bit. In the past 3 years, no matter when I encountered karma, situations, or demons, it was the wisdom of Master Lu's *Dharma in Plain Terms* that allowed me to overcome everything time and time again. So, we must learn more and read more about *Dharma in Plain Terms*.

My son was retributed in this life, the karmic obstacles on his body must be very heavy. Three feet of ice are not formed by a day's cold, so it is impossible to eliminate his karma in a short period. If one year is not enough, then two, three, or five years. The miracle lies in the accumulation of efforts every second and minute. Finally, quantitative changes reach qualitative changes.

Now the days are very full, very happy. I am grateful to have met such an excellent Dharma!

Dharma Practitioner: Q41

Comments

The boy's grandmother accumulated killing karma from slaughtering pigeons, and during pregnancy, the mother accumulated killing karma from eating live aquatic animals. Part of the killing karma from the elders will be repaid through the child. Additionally, the killing karma from banquets will be recorded onto the person for whom the banquet was held. Such an accumulation of heavy karma can eventually lead the boy to suffer from autism. A similar case was observed in a previous report [11].

Case 4. My autistic daughter's smooth transition to junior high school

1. Encountering the supreme Dharma Door, my autistic daughter finally started school

At the beginning of 2013, my daughter was almost five years old. She was lively, cute, smart, and sensible. However, after attending the funeral of a deceased relative, she began to exhibit behavioral, emotional, and sleep problems, which worsened over time. She was diagnosed with autism by two top-tier hospitals, beginning a long journey of seeking medical treatment. Following the doctors' advice, we took her to rehabilitation centers for training and administered traditional Chinese medicine.

At the end of 2014, a friend introduced me to the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, but due to my ignorance and unfamiliarity with it, I initially rejected it. As my daughter's condition deteriorated, we made another mistake by taking her to 9 different psychics in our hometown, hoping they could cure her. Predictably, the results were ineffective. Previously, we had also consulted 2 psychics. I deeply repent for our ignorance and apologize for our mistakes. We will diligently recite Buddhist scriptures, repay our karmic debts, eliminate our obstacles, and never repeat such foolish actions again.

In desperation, I remembered my friend's suggestion to recite Little Houses (a set of sutras and mantras). The next morning, I dreamt that the White-Robed Guan Yin Bodhisattva came to heal me, sprinkling sweet dew from a vase on me like raindrops. This strengthened my resolve to practice the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door.

In July 2015, I quickly obtained the Dharma Gems and started reciting Buddhist scriptures. Two weeks later, my husband joined me. We set up a Buddhist altar in September offered incense and recited Buddhist scriptures daily. Gradually, my daughter improved; her tantrums lessened, her sleep improved, and her behavioral issues decreased.

In September 2016, my daughter finally returned to school. Her grades improved, and she occasionally scored 100 points on tests (note: China uses the percentage grading system), much to our surprise! Seeing her progress, we became complacent and slacked off in our Dharma practices. We shifted our focus to her studies, putting a lot of pressure on her. After she finished the first grade, we spent the entire summer tutoring her, hoping she could skip a grade and catch up on the two years she missed (note: my daughter started elementary school in September 2014, but due to behavioral issues, she had to take a break after one semester and resumed first grade in September 2016).

2. Not understanding the true meaning of Buddhism, my daughter relapsed and dropped out

Due to the excessive tutoring, she was under tremendous pressure and didn't get a proper break during the entire summer. On November 4, 2017, she cried and refused to go to school. We still sent her to school intermittently. Master Lu enlightened us that children blessed by Bodhisattvas would do well if their parents diligently practiced Dharma, helped others, and performed good deeds. However, we forgot the Master's teachings!

Only now do I realize that my daughter's good performance from September 2016 to October 2017 was due to the blessings and protection of the Bodhisattvas and Master. Master Lu's Dharmakaya even blessed her three times in 2016. We should have diligently recited Buddhist scriptures, performed good deeds, and eliminated our karmic obstacles. Unfortunately, we went against Master's teachings and started using behavioral interventions, psychological counseling, and both Chinese and Western medicine. We spent 100,000 CNY (~\$14,000) in one year, but by December 2018, due to her emotional and behavioral issues, she could no longer attend school.

3. Grateful for Guan Yin Bodhisattva's mercy, my daughter's condition improved, and she entered junior high school

After reflecting on our mistakes, we decided to calm down and continue practicing Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door using the Four Golden Buddhist Practices and reciting Little Houses for her karmic creditors. Later, Bodhisattva mercifully provided guidance, and we were given medicine. After taking the medicine, my daughter stopped wetting herself the next day, and her emotional issues improved. Guan Yin Bodhisattva once said, "When a child calls for her mother, the mother hears." The Bodhisattva heard and mercifully offered my daughter the medicine. We are grateful to Guan Yin Bodhisattva, Master, and the fellow practitioner who delivered the medicine! By June 2020, I prayed to Guan Yin Bodhisattva to allow my daughter to attend school, even if it was a special school, so I could have the time and energy to recite Buddhist scriptures, repay karmic debts, and eliminate karmic obstacles. Subsequently, in dreams, it was revealed that to resolve our karmic conflicts with the school principal, we needed to recite 21 Little Houses, and for the class teacher, 49 Little Houses. After completing these, we recited an additional 21 Little Houses.

At the end of August 2020, after nearly two years away from elementary school, my daughter, under the compassionate arrangement of the Bodhisattvas, was admitted to a public experimental junior high school. The Bodhisattvas arranged for her a kind and understanding class teacher. She quickly adapted to junior high school life and completed the military training challenge despite previously being reluctant to exercise at home. She is happy daily, and her language and social skills have improved significantly. In her first three math exams, she scored 60 twice. Considering she only attended 2.5 years of elementary school and had been out of school for nearly 2 years, scoring 60 is quite satisfactory for us! In the midterm exams, out of 202 students, she ranked 195th. This is the miracle created by the Dharma!

Now, my daughter happily goes to school daily and occasionally gives stationery or handmade gifts to her close friends to strengthen their bond. Her class teacher says she is obedient and pretty, and the school's resource psychologist notes that she follows rules, loves studying, and reads a lot, though her grades are a bit behind. This is normal; even children who have attended six years of elementary school may not excel. As long as she works hard, her grades will improve. Therefore, I urge parents of children with

similar issues not to despair. If you believe in Guan Yin Bodhisattva, the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, and Master Lu, and diligently practice the "Four Golden Buddhist Practices," there will be a day when your child completely transforms!

As of today, we have been practicing for over five years and four months. I have been spreading the Dharma whenever possible and, with my husband, have recited Little Houses for sick relatives and over ten deceased relatives. We have recited nearly 7,500 Little Houses, including for aborted children, the karmic creditors of our house, our karmic creditors, deceased relatives, and 3,119 for our daughter's karmic creditors.

Dear fellow practitioners, we must spread the Dharma and help others while cultivating ourselves. We must become one of the hands and eyes of Guan Yin Bodhisattva and our compassionate master. Only then can we accumulate merits and virtues. With merits and virtues, the Bodhisattvas can use their divine powers to compassionately bless us and eliminate our karmic obstacles. Only then can our children, families, and careers improve, ultimately achieving perfection and liberation from the Six Realms of Reincarnation!

Dharma Practitioner: B42

Comments

1. Master Lu's opinion is that young children should not attend funerals, as it can negatively impact their mental health. He mentions that there have been instances where children developed psychological issues after attending such events. Instead, He suggests showing respect to the deceased by reciting Buddhist scriptures at home. He emphasizes that protecting the children's well-being is more important than adhering to traditional practices under familial pressure [29].
2. Master Lu advises against seeking help from psychics, as they can be influenced by spirits, which can bring negative consequences. He compares consulting a psychic to inviting a ghost into one's life, as psychics often have spirits attached to them, which gives them their abilities. He emphasizes that it's easy to invite a spirit but challenging to send it away, highlighting the importance of avoiding such practices altogether [30].

Case 5. Autistic Children Can Really Be Saved by Grasping This Opportunity!

Today, with deep gratitude and joy, I announce the good news. My child was diagnosed with developmental delay and high suspicion of autism at 1 year and 8 months. At the ages of 3 and 3.5, he was retested and found to have mild autism. However, at the age of 4, he successfully entered kindergarten, and his communication with other children and teachers became normal. The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is true, which saved my child from the autistic abyss. Although he still has some problems, I believe that as long as I adhere to the three Golden Buddhist Practices, he can completely recover and be on the right track!

I came into contact with Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door in 2012 when I was pregnant and had an unexpected miscarriage. I was very depressed. By then, Buddhist practitioner Li came to transform me. She sent me some information about the harms of miscarriage. Although I didn't believe in it 100%, I thought it wouldn't hurt to recite some Buddhist scriptures. I started using my commuting time to do my daily recitation and recite Little Houses. At that time, I didn't intend to read *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, and I didn't listen to

Master Lu's recordings. I didn't want to let my friends know I believed in Buddhism. After reciting Buddhist scriptures for a while, I felt some effects. My allergic rhinitis, which had not been cured for 20 years, had obviously improved. Thus, I continued to recite Buddhist scriptures, and I also released many lives every month.

At the end of 2012, I got pregnant again. My parents came over to care for me. When they realized that I had vowed to be a vegetarian for 2 days a month, they objected to it. They advised me not to be a vegetarian for the sake of the baby. Hence, I violated my vegetarian vow in the latter part of my pregnancy and during breastfeeding. They stewed pigeons and fish in soup from time to time to provide me with "nutritious food". I foolishly thought this would be healthy for the baby and ate them all. In retrospect, I realized how costly it was to break a vow. I broke my vow and ate meat for my child, so how could the child be well?

Within a month after my child was born, I found out he had an umbilical hernia, a hemangioma, and colic. When he was older than a month, I found out he had severe eczema. When he was 100 days old, he had rotavirus diarrhea. He had diarrhea >10 times a day. He had to be hospitalized and given fluids to recover. In summary, he was in a constant state of discomfort. I started reciting Little House to his karmic creditors, but only a dozen or so until he turned 1 year old.

Just after he turned 1 year old, he got a serious illness - pneumonia. He was hospitalized in our hometown county hospital for 5 days to supply him with fluids, and then recovered and was discharged. We took him to the city hospital for 10 days after his pneumonia relapsed. After that, he was released from the hospital and took antibiotics for a week. His illness relapsed 5 days after stopping the medication. This time, we traveled to the provincial capital hospital to see the outpatient clinic. The doctor said my child is weak and very severe. The doctor wrote a note for my child to get in and admit him to the hospital! On the first day, he breathed >60 times per minute. Oxygen did not help. The nurse drew arterial blood from the base of his thigh to check whether his organs had been affected by oxygen shortage. The arterial blood was dark red. The doctor said that he did not even need to do any tests to determine that the oxygen level in the blood was too low. On the spot, the doctor transferred him to the intensive care unit and gave us a serious illness notice.

I had no choice but to call Dharma practitioner Li for help. She immediately promised to help me release lives early the next morning. She advised me to make a big vow. I moved to the hospital corridor and vowed to the Bodhisattva while crying:

1. Donate money to print 1,000 Buddhist Recitation Collections in 1 month.
2. Perform life liberation every month for my child for the rest of my life.
3. Recite 100 Little Houses for my child in 6 months.
4. Be a vegetarian for 1 year.
5. After my child recovers, I will convince sentient beings to practice Buddhism using his experiences.

After making the vow, I walked back to the hospital room and heard the nurse say that his respiration rate had dropped to about 30 breaths per minute. This meant he didn't need a ventilator but just continued to take oxygen and observe him. Guan Yin Bodhisattva heard my prayers and manifested! I didn't

dare slack off at night and kept reciting the *Great Compassion Mantra* for him until the next morning. He didn't wake up in the morning. Practitioner Li and some enthusiastic practitioners called me. They said they were releasing the lives for my child, and asked me to recite the Buddhist scriptures synchronously. I recited Buddhist scriptures according to the life liberation ritual. Half an hour later, he woke up. He ate an apple and porridge. Then he got up in good spirits.

That night before, because my child was in a very bad condition, I called his father while crying. His father took the first flight in the morning. When he saw our child eating in good spirits, he asked me with a puzzled look on his face why I needed him to come back since our child was doing so well. He hadn't been there for the difficult 10 hours, so he could hardly understand how devastated and helpless I felt at that time. Later on, my child's test results showed no abnormalities in any organs except the heart. A heart problem was detected the same day when blood was drawn. The next day he recovered miraculously. Even the doctor was shocked. He could be discharged earlier. In this way, he recovered successfully under Bodhisattva's mercy. I thought everything would be fine after that, but I didn't realize even greater difficulties were waiting for me.

In April 2015, when he was 1.5 years old, I found that his intellectual development was obviously much slower than that of other children. He didn't pay much attention to what he was told to do. When he wanted something, he banged his head against the wall if he wasn't satisfied immediately. I searched the Internet to find out what the problem with banging was. I saw an article that said banging is one of autism's manifestations. I clicked on it to see how many symptoms were consistent with those described therein. I was so scared that I told my husband. At first, my husband said I was just worrying about it. After he did a search on his own he stopped talking. We immediately made an appointment to take him to the hospital.

On May 4, 2015, we traveled to a child health agency. Test results indicate that his intelligence is only 8 months old, he has a developmental delay of 1 year, and he is highly suspected of autism. The doctor said something that I still remember vividly: "This child will not have a future, so you parents should be prepared for that." I was in tears on the spot. My child was only 1.5 years old. How could he be judged for the rest of his life?

Unwilling to give up, I sought information online. The more I searched, the more desperate I became. At that time, I really felt there was no way to live. I would cry bitterly at the sight of any child on the road. Then I stopped searching for information and logged on to Master Lu's blog every day to read His teachings and fellow practitioners' sharing presentations. I read them over and over again. Then I said to myself, "It doesn't matter, I still have the Dharma. Since so many practitioners have created miracles through the Dharma, why can't I create one?" After half a month of depression, I picked myself up and started to walk on two legs. On the one hand, I planned the number of Little Houses to recite every day, vowing 1,000 Little Houses for his creditors. On the other hand, I traveled with my husband to find a rehabilitation center to intervene. We searched for several good rehab centers in our area, but we had to wait in line for 0.5 years, 1 year, and 1.5 years. Buddha blessed us and let us find a rehab center that had just opened. The teacher had just come out of a famous center. So, we signed up on the spot. We immediately went to the rehab center to start our intervention. The night before we set up the Buddhist altar in the house we rented next to the rehab

center, I had my first dream about Master Lu. He was in a tall pagoda reading totems for us. He said to me, all your difficulties are just temporary! Certainly, everything will get better. This dream gave me much confidence. Now more than 2 years have passed, he is over 4 years old, and he has been in kindergarten for more than 3 months now. The teacher's comments on him: "When entering kindergarten he can take the initiative to greet the teacher, raising his hands in class is very active, outdoor activities he likes to cooperate with friends, he can apologize for doing something wrong, seeing someone crying he will go up to comfort. Many children say he is their closest friend." I was moved really to tears. Of course, from my point of view, he still has some autistic traits. However, I was confident that these issues would be resolved as I repented and paid off the karmic debts. By the time he starts elementary school, Bodhisattva will surely bless him to keep up with the pace of elementary school.

In The Following, I Would Like to Discuss My Understanding and Lessons I Have Learned From Practicing Buddhism In The Past Few Years

1. Pay Off your Debts and Eliminate Karmic Obstacles During the Smooth Time. First of all, I came into contact with Buddhism before the onset of karmic obstacles. I am deeply grateful to the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva and practitioner Li who transformed me. Although I didn't know much about Buddhism at the beginning, it saved me when I went through the biggest shock of my life. Like many parents of autistic children, I had thoughts of suicide. If I hadn't stayed in front of the computer every day to read Master Lu's blog and presentations from Buddhist practitioners, I might have done something irreversible. It was the Master and fellow practitioners who gave me great courage. Hence, any practitioners in trouble should also have this faith. Since there are so many practitioners who have created miracles through Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, why can't we do the same? In addition, I recited some Little Houses to myself before the outbreak of my karmic obstacles. I also insisted on releasing lives. When I started to recite Little Houses to my child, his stagnation period was shorter, approximately 300 Little Houses resulting in obvious progress. Therefore, please don't wait until your karmic obstacles explode before practicing Buddhism. Instead, pay off your debts and eliminate karmic obstacles during smooth times.

2. I Realized How Heavy My Karma was After Practicing Buddhism Before learning Buddhism, I always thought I was a good person who deserved a good reward. However, after learning Buddhism, I realized how heavy my karma was. My parents owned a restaurant when I was young, so my ancestors' killing karma was already very severe. I never stopped eating chicken, ducks, and fish as a child. Furthermore, I only ate the best part of everything. In my school days, I loved to read romance novels, and then I read internet novels, so I had a very heavy sexual karma. When I was pregnant, I broke the precepts and violated the vow for the sake of my baby. My child has been punished by retribution for the wrongs I have committed. If I hadn't studied Buddhism, I would have continued further down the wrong path. Now I know that I have to detach myself, keep the precepts, let go, learn not to create new karma, keep eliminating old karma, pay off small karmic debts, and have faith in the future even though it is very difficult now, which is the most worthwhile thing I should be doing.

3. Difficulties and Adversities are Contributory Conditioning Power

Although I encountered Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door in 2012, I didn't practice very seriously when things were fine and well. At that time, practitioner Li who transformed me, talked to me several times about setting up a Buddhist altar and becoming a vegetarian. However, I didn't do it because I thought it would be too difficult to do it. I didn't dare imagine being a vegetarian forever at that time. Although I vowed to be a vegetarian 2 days a month, sometimes I forgot to do so, and this was strongly opposed by my family. However, from the time my child had pneumonia, step by step, I set up the Buddhist altar and made up my mind to be a vegetarian. Because my family strongly objected to vegetarianism before, I only vowed to be a vegetarian for 5 years for the time being. When I brought my child home in August, my family's opposition voice was quieter than before. Now I am overcoming my introversion and lack of self-confidence. I transform sentient beings on the street. Every difficulty pulls me towards the right path. Every firm step I take in Buddhism is made possible by my child. Please cherish the Buddha's affinity that adversity brings to us.

4. The Only Way I Can Save My Child is to Practice Buddhism and Never Slack Off.

To learn Buddhism, we need to read more books by Master Lu, read more blogs by Master Lu, listen to more recordings by Master Lu, and watch more shared stories by fellow practitioners. The more you understand the principle of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, the easier it is to persevere. Although the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door has given me many efficacious experiences, I still have doubts and have slacked 2 times in the past 2 years.

The first time I slacked off reciting Buddhist scriptures happened in 2017. At the beginning of 2016, in order to train my child well, I attended some seminars and read some books on intervention. They said that the ages between 2-6 years old are the children's golden time. In order to achieve better results, parents must seize every moment to communicate with children and intervene. This made me skeptical about reciting Buddhist scriptures. I spent all day reciting Buddhist scriptures without much communication training with my child. Would it miss the golden training period? With this thinking in mind, I began to slack off reciting Buddhist scriptures. Consequently, my child soon regressed, forgetting the things he had learned at the rehab center. I learned from this painful experience and began to recite Buddhist scriptures diligently again, and soon he made progress again.

The second time I slacked off reciting Buddhist scriptures happened from January to April 2017. Apart from reciting Buddhist scriptures, I also did intervention programs for my child as stated above. He had been consistently making progress. At that time, I thought that his progress was due to the treatment programs and not to my reciting the Little House. Once again, I slacked on reciting Buddhist scriptures. From January onwards, the Little House recitation almost stopped. In mid-May, we did a test, and the results were bad. Many indices were at a standstill or regressing. The test results showed he was still mildly autistic. I was very frustrated!

It was just then, that I received a phone call from the Australia Oriental Media (because I had made a reservation the year before for Master Lu to read my child's totem). Master Lu enlightened me that my child needed 1,350 Little Houses. So far, my child's creditors received 800 Little Houses (at the time, I recited 1,300-1,400 Little Houses for his creditors). So, I needed to recite 550 more Little Houses. As a result of the test report from doctors and the enlightenment from Master Lu, I had to reconsider the relationship between

Buddhist intervention and rehab interventions. I finally woke up that only Buddhism could save my child, and that all other therapies are, at the most, just icing on the cake. If taking away the root of reciting Buddhist scriptures, other treatments can only alleviate some of the child's symptoms at best. In other words, rehab interventions will not be able to make him normal.

To date, I have repaid all of the Little Houses Master Lu has revealed to me about my son's debts. From May to August, his change was subversive. At the end of May, during the kindergarten interview, he pooped in his pants, rolled around on the ground, and did not answer the teacher a question (I was afraid that the teacher would see that something was wrong with him, but the teacher didn't care, which I believe it was the Buddha's blessing)! On August 20, when the teacher visited me, he improved a lot. His behavior was very pleasant, almost normal. Additionally, he was previously found to have severe allergies to many foods that affected his intelligence. He fasted on those foods all the time. His entry into kindergarten made me very concerned. After he started kindergarten, he was no longer allergic to many foods except for a couple of them. Now, we let him eat freely. No obvious regressions or emotional problems occurred. Everything has been arranged for me by the Bodhisattva perfectly!

Now I look back on the experience of these 2 years, although I arranged him a lot of various so-called scientific treatment programs, every time he made great progress, when I recited Buddhist scriptures very diligently, every time my child had stagnation or even regression, is when I slacked off. There were also many times when I recommended my child's very effective scientific treatment program to my non-Buddhist friends. No one found it to be very effective when they tried it. It worked for me, but not for my non-Buddhist friends. Isn't this Buddha's blessing for my child? I was able to achieve 100% or even 200% effect in every effort that I made to help my child because of Buddha's compassionate blessing! Dharma is the foundation!

5. Little House Quality is More Critical than Quantity. At the beginning, to catch up with the number of Little Houses, I recited 5-7 sheets a day. The *Great Compassion Mantra* was reduced from 50 seconds to 45 seconds and to 35 seconds per recitation. The *Heart Sutra* was also reduced to about 20 seconds long per recitation. When I talked to fellow practitioners, I was complacent that I could recite more Buddhist scriptures in the same amount of time. Although some practitioners dream that my Little House quality was problematic, I have not been concerned. In May this year, when I received Master Lu's call, I had already recited >1,300 Little Houses. However, Master Lu said that my child's creditors had only received 800 sheets. Since then, I have taken it seriously. Later, when I checked the Buddhist scriptures, I found that I had missed words in both the *Great Compassion Mantra* and the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra*. I hastened to recite the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* 27 times to repent of these wrongdoings. In fact, I found that catching up in quantity wasn't worth the effort. Good quality Little Houses would have been more efficient.

6. Please Emphasize the Power of Propagating the Dharma Via our Experiences.

A while ago, I called the Australian Oriental Media. The fellow practitioner who answered the phone gave me an example after understanding my situation. A mother of a child with cerebral palsy was very diligent in helping her child recite 2,000 Little Houses. However, the child did not change much. She then stepped out onto the streets to transform people into Buddhists. She found that her child made progress every day. The practitioner of Australia Oriental Media told me to not only recite Buddhist scriptures but

also transform sentient beings. Propagating the Dharma has greater merits and virtues than reciting Buddhist scriptures. In November, I began using the Internet to convince sentient beings to practice Buddhism using my experiences. It was amazing to me that my child had become more agile. All three of his teachers have given me feedback from different perspectives on how much he has improved over the past 2 weeks. Buddha is so compassionate. As long as we make a bit of effort, we will receive more rewards. I will continue to propagate Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door and use my own personal experience of Buddhism to help more sentient beings believe in Buddhism and persevere in practicing Buddhism.

Dear fellow Dharma practitioners, if you encounter the Dharma in good times, the Dharma can help you reduce or even eliminate the thorns that you may meet in the future so that your life can be smoother; if you encounter the Dharma in adversity, the Dharma can fundamentally change the adversity that you are now in; if you are uncertain, doubtful, confused in the process of practicing the Dharma, please persevere for a little while longer, and the Dharma will give you unlimited surprises.

I hope that my sharing today can give you more confidence and courage so that we can move forward on the right path together steadily.

Dharma Practitioner: N43

Comments

1. After making a vow, you must fulfill it and not break it; otherwise, the consequences will be significant. For example, if you vow to become a vegetarian but later regret it and eat meat again, the consequences will be severe. Breaking a vow is equivalent to deceiving the Bodhisattva [31].

2. The practitioner, a thoughtful, conscientious, and rational mother, carefully compared Dharma practices with scientific rehabilitation programs to determine which had the most significant positive impact on her child's autism. This presentation offers valuable insights for medical professionals, parents of autistic children, and anyone concerned with neurological health.

Discussion

When autism remains a global challenge for a cure, Dharma offers a solution to completely eradicate it. Through five cases that replicated our previous report [11], along with numerous other reports of ASD being healed [12], we can confidently assert that the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door can indeed cure autism. This stands in contrast to previous sporadic reports where children spontaneously recovered from autism without a clear explanation or where the results could not be replicated [8,9]. Within the Dharma framework, these recoveries are easily explained: once the spirit has settled its karmic debts, it departs. When the spirit leaves, the patient naturally recovers.

Science seeks to understand the mechanisms behind how and why children develop autism. Similarly, Dharma aims to reveal the underlying principles of cause and effect. Let's use one of the causes of abortion as an example to explore how and why children may develop autism. As previously mentioned, life is composed of both a physical body and a soul [11,32]. After an abortion or miscarriage, the soul of the aborted child departs from its physical body and becomes a spirit. Since the spirit's natural lifespan has not yet ended, it cannot reincarnate or return to the underworld. These spirits often remain attached to the mother or her other children. If attached to the mother, this can lead to physical and emotional issues, including gynecological problems. If attached to the mother's other children, it can cause rebellious behavior and neurodevelopmental health issues, such as

autism. This occurs because the spirit of the aborted child harbors resentment and seeks revenge, causing the other children in the family to suffer from autism, which in turn brings pain to the mother.

This outcome of abortion can be understood within the framework of karmic retribution. But what about spirits that were not directly harmed by you? For example, when children come into contact with spirits by playing spiritual games, those spirits can attach themselves to the children and potentially cause issues like autism [33]. As the saying goes, "One who stays near vermilion gets stained red; one who stays near ink gets stained black." Master Lu repeatedly emphasizes that spirits enter our lives only when there is a karmic connection. When children play spiritual games, they essentially befriend spirits, forming affinities with them. Consequently, it is only natural that spirits may occupy the children's bodies. Therefore, while we should respect spirits, we must also keep our distance from them [34]. Children should avoid engaging in spiritual games, and parents should refrain from consulting psychics, as psychics are often influenced by spirits.

Master Lu advises against allowing grandparents to raise children, as this can diminish the child's good fortune and blessings. Additionally, when grandparents pass away, their spirits may attach to the child, potentially leading to conditions like autism. For instance, a boy born in 2001, the Year of the Snake, developed autism due to the attachment of his deceased grandmother's spirit [35]. Similarly, a girl born in 2000, the Year of the Loong, developed autism because her deceased grandfather's spirit became attached to her [36].

Spirits contribute not only to autism but also to a wide range of other conditions, including schizophrenia, epilepsy, vertigo, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, leukemia, paralysis, temporomandibular joint dislocation [11], Alzheimer's disease (AD) [32], oncogene activation [11,37], asthma [38], genetic diseases [39], avascular necrosis of the femoral head, Parkinson's disease, arthritis, migraines, pharyngitis [40], various skin conditions [11,41], depression [11,40,42], mouth disease [43], and more.

It is noteworthy that the majority of neurological health concerns may be linked to the presence of spirits within the brain. When spirits impact the brain, the effects often extend to the gut, as the gut's nervous system is intricately connected to the central nervous system. Moreover, spirits can directly affect the gut by traveling from the brain to this region. As a result, alterations in gut microbiota [44] may be better understood as symptoms influenced by spirits, rather than the root cause. Similarly, spirits may disrupt cellular genetic material, implying that the genetic changes observed in patients with autism [3] could also represent symptoms rather than fundamental causes. The five successful cases highlighted in this article, along with an additional case detailed in a prior review paper [11], underscore this perspective. By extension, the potential efficacy of other therapeutic interventions, such as deep brain stimulation (DBS) [7], can also be anticipated with relative confidence.

Treating the symptoms of autism still holds value. For instance, managing primary healthcare and routine minor procedures for children with ASD can be challenging. In such cases, pharmacological sedation may be necessary to help control their behavior. Although these medications can have side effects, they are sometimes essential for managing the condition [45].

Ultimately, the key to addressing autism lies in helping the spirit leave the child. The Five Golden Buddhist Practices can be employed to assist in guiding the spirits of aborted children and other types of spirits to ascend.

This approach has proven effective in our previous reports on various stubborn diseases [11,32, 37-43].

During the decades that Master Lu devoted to spreading the Dharma, He left behind a vast collection of audio, video, and written materials, all of which eventually focus on the concept of karma. In fact, humanity is constantly living within the framework of cause and effect. The experiences of Master Lu's followers in practicing Dharma also demonstrate that the law of cause and effect is undeniably real and that the spiritual realm truly exists. For instance, a daughter once said to her parents, "Ah? Are you going to recite 49 Little Houses?" (Case 1). Another example is how a grandfather, despite being separated from his granddaughter by great distances, somehow knew that she was helping him through Guan Yin Bodhisattva [32]. Denying the existence of the spiritual realm is truly unfortunate because it leaves one helpless against the harm that comes from it, which is the karmic retribution for the harm you've caused others in the past. Denying the existence of the spiritual realm also means denying the harm you've done to others, which prevents you from overcoming your current difficulties—such as being unable to cure your child's autism.

Some individuals possess significant wisdom, even if they are not part of the academic community, such as the Dharma practitioner of the gout presentation [11] and the practitioner of Case 5. In their efforts to alleviate their children's suffering, they either actively or passively engaged in comparative studies with a scientific approach. The author of the gout presentation compared conventional medical treatments with Dharma methods, identifying which approach primarily addresses symptoms and which one targets the root cause. Similarly, the author of Case 5 compared intervention therapies with Dharma practices in treating her son's autism, discerning which method fundamentally addresses the condition and which one serves as a supplementary measure.

The essence of Dharma is grounded in two principles: compassion and wisdom. The introduction of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door to the world represents a compassionate effort to relieve the suffering of sentient beings. Practicing Dharma is a path to cultivating wisdom, but wisdom cannot be simply conferred by others. For example, when Dharma practitioner N33 initially heard that Dharma had cured a fellow practitioner's asthma [38], she was skeptical and dismissed others' successes. It was only after her own asthma was cured that the effectiveness of Dharma became clear to her. Similarly, when it is suggested that Dharma can alleviate a child's autism, many readers remain doubtful, citing various reasons for their skepticism, which hinders them from gaining wisdom. In contrast, parents who have successfully treated their children's autism by practicing the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door have gained wisdom through their personal experience. Thus, wisdom can only be acquired through personal experience and cannot be instilled by others [11]. This truth was taught to Buddhist followers 2,500 years ago by the Buddha.

A long-standing question that has puzzled the medical community may now have an answer: Why do some children with autism display extraordinary talents in specific areas? According to Master Lu's teachings, this is because the spirits attached to these children were skilled in those fields during their previous lives. For instance, if a spirit attached to a child with autism was once an artist, musician, or mathematician, the child may naturally exhibit artistic talents, musical abilities, or exceptional mathematical skills. These spirits may even display greater capabilities than they had in life due to

possessing one or more of the five magic powers [41]. Similarly, if the spirit attached to an autistic child is vain, the child will enjoy hearing flattering words (Q&A 2). If the spirit studied Buddhism in a previous life, the child may naturally begin reciting Buddhist scriptures from a young age [20]. If the spirit is that of a tiger, the child might mimic the sounds of a tiger, behave like one, or even claw at his mother [24]. Once the spirit leaves the autistic patient, these savant-like abilities and other unusual behaviors will disappear, leading to the child's recovery.

No matter how talented an external spirit may be, the brain and nervous system should always be under the control of one's own soul, much like how we previously discussed this concept using a car as a metaphor [11]. The integration of soul and body defines the true self, the person who is genuinely the child of their parents. Those with autism, whose brains and nervous systems have already been taken over by external spirits, similar to those observed in AD patients [32], are no longer able to change their situation. Support from parents and relatives becomes crucial in initiating positive change. Historically, some eminent monks and virtuous practitioners could perceive the spirits attached to patients, but without this Dharma Door and without the "Little House," they were powerless to help. Now, we have the "Little House" and can use it to ascend spirits. You are fortunate to have this opportunity to liberate your child from spirit's control. Seize this chance to change the fate of your child and your entire family.

Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is a miraculous remedy of compassion bestowed by Guan Yin Bodhisattva during the Age of Dharma Decline to save sentient beings. The mind is the lock, and the Dharma Door is the key. Using the Dharma Door to unlock your mind is called "Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door."

Recovery

To learn how to recover from autism through reciting Buddhist scriptures, there are two Q&A programs where Master Lu provides guidance.

Q&A 3: How can children with autism recover [46]?

Listener: Why were there fewer children with autism in the past, and now there are more and more? From the perspective of Buddhism, what kind of karmic obstacles cause this?

Master: In the past, we hadn't yet entered the Age of Dharma Decline, but now we have.

Listener: Right.

Master: In the past, there weren't as many karmic obstacles, but now they are accumulating more and more! Let me give you a simple example: In a previous life, two people were a couple, and they fought and quarreled, creating resentment; in the next life, they fought and quarreled even more intensely; In this life, they started quarreling before they even got married. Isn't the resentment growing more and more?

Listener: Yes.

Master: So, what is autism? Autism is caused by spirit possession—it's the spirits coming to collect debts! The more debts were owed from past quarrels and fights, the more the spirits came to collect in this life. If your child is born with autism, it means that a spirit is already targeting your child, causing chaos in your household! Because you owe a lot, the spirit comes to trouble you.

Listener: A fellow practitioner has already recited 1,000 Little Houses for her child's karmic creditors, and there has been significant improvement, but

sometimes there are still relapses, and when they happen, they are severe.

What is the reason for this?

Master: Relapses are normal. For example, if you have a fever and take medicine to suppress it, but stop taking the medicine for a while, or if the dosage reaches a certain point and you stop, there will be a rebound, just like high blood pressure. After the rebound, you must continue taking the medicine and continue reciting Buddhist scriptures. When people take antibiotics, doctors often tell them to finish the entire course to completely eliminate the bacteria; only then can they stop. Some people stop after taking just a few pills because the toothache or fever has improved, thinking everything is fine. But when they stop, there's a sudden rebound.

Listener: I understand, it becomes more severe.

Master: Exactly, of course, it will. Not taking enough medicine.

Listener: Yes, after reciting 1,000 Little Houses, they should continue to vow to recite more in batches until full recovery.

Master: Yes, keep reciting. This issue requires continuous effort until it's completely resolved. If it's not completely resolved, then it's not resolved at all.

Listener: Thank you, master.

Q&A 4: How to recite Buddhist scriptures for children with autism [47]?

Listener: A fellow Buddhist practitioner's son was born with autism and is now 7 years old. The child cannot communicate with others, and he doesn't understand what others say, living in his own world. His mother is very sad. In this situation, should she recite 49 times of the *Heart Sutra* and fewer times of the *Great Compassion Mantra* for her son?

Master: Yes.

Listener: Can he recite the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Great Repentance* five times for her son?

Master: Yes, it must be five times.

Listener: Should the Little Houses be recited continuously and in large numbers?

Master: Yes.

Listener: I previously heard you say that autism requires at least 1,000 Little Houses. If this fellow practitioner wants to make a vow regarding the number of Little Houses, should she vow in batches of 49 or 108, or should she vow 1,000 or more all at once?

Master: Make a large vow but fulfill it in smaller batches. Tell them that you'll repay \$10,000, but each week, you'll pay \$100.

Additionally, letting the child expose the back to sunlight to increase their positive energy can be helpful for children with autism [15]. At night, keep a small light on in the child's room and the hallway, using a warm-colored light [48].

Prevention

In ancient China, the legendary physician Que Bian (407 BCE - 310 BCE) was widely known for his medical expertise. According to historical accounts, King Wen of Wei once inquired of Que Bian, "Que Bian, you and your two brothers are all highly skilled in medicine. Who among you is the most proficient?" Que Bian humbly replied, "Your Majesty, my eldest brother is the most skilled, my second brother is next, and I am the least skilled."

Curious, King Wen asked, "Why, then, are you the most famous?" Que Bian explained, "My eldest brother treats illnesses before they manifest. Because

people are unaware that he has already removed the ailment beforehand, his reputation does not spread far and wide. My second brother treats illnesses in their early stages, so people believe he only cures minor ailments, and his reputation is known only locally. As for me, I treat illnesses when they have become severe. People assume my medical skills are the highest, and therefore, my fame spreads throughout the country [49]."

This ancient anecdote underscores a critical principle in healthcare: the importance of proactive prevention. Addressing health issues before they arise is key to maintaining well-being. In the context of autism, this principle can be applied by taking measures to prevent the underlying causes from manifesting.

Given the clear understanding of autism's causes, it is possible to adopt behaviors that mitigate the risk of developing this condition. Specifically, practices that prevent the generation of negative karma can effectively reduce the likelihood of autism. The following guidelines are suggested to minimize the risk:

1. **Avoid Killing:** Refrain from maternal abortions, the killing of animals by parents, and the consumption of live aquatic animals. Do not hold banquets in a child's name that involve the killing of animals, particularly aquatic creatures.
2. **Spiritual Caution:** Ensure that children avoid playing spiritual games. Ensure that parents avoid seeking help from psychics.
3. **Limit Exposure to Spiritual Environments:** Prevent children from visiting places frequently inhabited by spirits, such as cemeteries or funerals.
4. **Foster a Harmonious Family Environment to Promote Well-being:** Parents and children should prioritize both physical and neurological health. Parents should create a peaceful family atmosphere, avoiding quarrels or discussions of divorce in the presence of children.
5. **Encourage Sunlight Exposure:** Participate in outdoor activities to allow children to receive adequate sunlight on their backs.
6. **Reduce Academic Pressure:** Parents should avoid placing excessive learning pressure on children, maintain realistic academic expectations, and be content with the child's achievements. Encourage more and criticize less.
7. **Address Predestined Calamities:** During critical ages, such as 369 [11], recite Little Houses to assist the child's karmic creditors.
8. **Keep your vows:** For Dharma practitioners, it is important not to break vows.
9. **Continue practicing Buddhism to prevent relapse [50]:** After the autism is cured, indicating that the spirit has departed, ceasing the recitation of Buddhist scriptures may invite other spirits to take its place. These spirits may sense that the individual is vulnerable, and, recognizing a familiar environment, they could attach themselves again, potentially leading to a relapse. The departure of the spirit associated with ASD does not necessarily indicate that all karma has been eradicated. In fact, substantial residual karma may still be present. When this karma resurfaces, it increases the likelihood of attracting other spirits, which could result in a recurrence of symptoms.

However, don't be intimidated by karma. As long as you continue practicing Dharma and avoid creating new karma, your karma will decrease, just like paying off a mortgage. Eventually, the proportion of karmic obstacles will fall below 10%, allowing one to attain the Four Sagely Realms [11].

Children represent the future of humanity. To ensure a bright future and prevent suffering in the next generation, it is essential to follow Master Lu's preventive guidelines and actively work to eliminate karma. Moreover, a multidisciplinary, society-wide effort must come together to protect and care for children. By doing this, we can shield future generations from challenges such as autism. Let us unite to safeguard the well-being of our children.

Conclusion

Autism remains a significant global challenge, with its causes and cures largely eluding scientific understanding. However, within the framework of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, autism can be addressed through Dharma practices. The Dharma approach explains that autism and other neurological or mental health issues can result from spirits attached to a child due to karmic debts, often originating from actions like abortion or other karmic transgressions. By practicing the Five Golden Buddhist Practices, individuals can eliminate these karmic debts and guide spirits to ascend, thereby curing conditions like autism. While preventive measures can help reduce the likelihood of new autism-related karma, complete eradication of the condition requires diligent Dharma practice to remove existing karma. This holistic approach not only offers a path to recovery but also emphasizes the importance of proactive prevention for the well-being of future generations.

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Conflict of Interest

No.

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Ethical Statement

The author did not involve any part of the experimental design, experimental treatments, and result analysis of the 5 patients. All the experimental procedures and practices by the 5 presenters were done by themselves independently.

Statement by Translator and Writer

The 5 stories and 4 Q&A dialogues from Master Lu's blog were translated from Chinese to English based on their intended meaning rather than a word-for-word approach. The remaining portions of the paper were written based on my limited understanding of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. If there are any inaccuracies or deviations from the true meaning of the Chinese version, or if the content does not accurately reflect Master Lu's teachings, I sincerely seek forgiveness from the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva, all Buddhas and Bodhisattvas, Dharma Protectors, and Master Jun Hong Lu.

Disclaimer of Liability

The contents of the presentation, comments, and discussion, including text, images, and other information obtained from Dharma practitioners, are provided strictly for reference purposes. Due to the unique nature of

individual karma, results similar to those experienced by the practitioners may not be replicated. The experiences and advice shared should not be construed as medical advice or a diagnosis.

In the event of an emergency, it is crucial to promptly contact your doctor or emergency services by dialing 911. Relying on any information found in this paper is done solely at your own risk. The author bears no responsibility for the consequences. By using or misusing the contents, you accept liability for any personal injury, including death. It is imperative to exercise caution and seek professional medical guidance for health-related concerns.

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